

Place of Hotels in Tourism and Some Problems of It

Tukhliev Iskandar Suyunovich

Doctor of economic science, professor, department of Tourism of Samarkand institute of economy and service, Samarkand city 140100, Amir Temur street 9

Azamatova Nozima Jaxongirovna

Master student of faculty tourism and service Samarkand institute of economy and service Samarkand city 140100, Amir Temur street 9

Abstract: Nowadays, hotels play an important role in tourism field when it comes to especially attracting tourists. The most well-known hotels, particularly, relied on tourists as a source of financial benefits. However, some problems might be seen and drawbacks should be fixed in the future. Tourism and hospitality are indispensable part of sphere.

Key points: hospitality, tourists, hotels, motels, hospitable, greeting, dictionaries, grudge, effort, reception, courteous services.

Introduction

Hotels are treated as a main part of tourism as well as motels are becoming popular. Tourism industry is relied on hospitality as a main source of attracting tourists. Especially, west countries. Hospitality is treating people like you would want to be treated when you are traveling. In other words, it means making a tourist feel totally welcome not only as your guest but also as the guest of the complete family of the Hotel. Hospitality is a genuine smiling face. Hospitality can be termed as a deliberate, planned and sustained effort to establish and maintain mutual understanding between an organization and the public i.e., the business of making and keeping friends, and promoting an atmosphere of better understanding. The Oxford English Dictionary defines it as “the act or practice of being hospitable; the reception and entertainment of guests, visitors or strangers”. The word hospitality is derived from the Latin word “Hospitalitas” very frequently we hear phrases like “He is always hospitable to his visitors”, “We are grateful to friends for their hospitality in putting us up while we were on holiday”, “She is so inhospitable that she grudges giving us anything to eat or drink when we visit her”, etc. All such statements are suggesting a positive or negative attitude of welcome towards visitors; friends or strangers. Hospitality activity covers everything, providing attentive and courteous services, facilities and amenities to a traveller, meeting and greeting him at the door, providing efficient and caring service of food and beverage to him in his room i.e., providing “A Home away from Home”, and making his visit a memorable and pleasant experience.

Reception, welcome and, the treatment of a guest or a stranger in the most friendly manner is Hospitality. In most of the countries all over the world, a guest is received with a great amount of courtesy and warmth and is provided with entertainment. The basic concept of Hospitality is to make the guest feel that he has come amongst friends and that. Although the basic concept of hospitality has remained the same, yet with the passage of time and development of technology and science, the needs and wants of travellers have changed greatly thus providing numerous services

and facilities in terms of accommodation and other basic needs such as food and beverages. In olden days kings, lords, maharajas, landlords, and sometimes the panchayats used to provide food and shelter to travellers and their animals free of charge and it used to be a benevolent activity. But with the passage of time, it has not only remained a benevolent activity but has also become a flourishing business(1). Early travelers were either warriors or traders or people in search of knowledge and there were no hotels. Warriors and conquerors pitched their tents for accommodation while traders and persons traveling for knowledge placed a high value on hospitality and sometimes traded their merchandise for lodging.

Inn keeping can be said to be the first commercial enterprise for hospitality and one of the first services for which money was exchanged. Inns of the Biblical times offered only a cot or a bench in the corner. Guests stayed in large communal rooms with no sanitation and privacy. The rates were, of course, reasonable. The company was rough. Travellers shared the same quarters with their horses and animals.

A hotel management contract is defined as an agreement between a management company (or an operator), and a property owner, whereby the operator assumes responsibility for managing the property by providing direction, supervision, and expertise through established methods and procedures. The operator runs the hotel, on behalf of the owner, for a fee, according to specified terms negotiated with the owner. Negotiating the terms of a hotel management contract should not be approached lightly, as it can characterize the property's identity for decades and produce differing results for owners. A well-negotiated management agreement should align the interests of both parties. As an owner, the major goals should be to select the management company that will maximize profitability and therefore the value of the asset and to secure the best possible contract terms with that operator, while at the same time ensuring the operator is properly incentivized to maximize profitability(2).

History Of Hotels And Accommodation Industry And Their Development

The early history of accommodation for travellers can be traced back to the Greek word 'Xenia', which not only meant hospitality but also the protection given to a traveller from discomforts. The city was bound to offer hospitality. In Sparta city, although due to rigorous customs visitors were not encouraged, yet goddess Athena was considered as the protector of strangers and hence her name was 'Xenia Athena'.

In this period travellers were mainly diplomats, philosophers, intellectuals and researchers. Guests were invited to stay with noblemen. In ancient Olympia, buildings constructed with the aim to accommodate strangers can be seen. They were called 'Leonidio' and were built in 4th century BC. The concept of hospitality can also be drawn back to ancient times. Mention of it is found in 'Iliad' and 'The Odyssey' by Homer(3).

During the seventh and eighth centuries, it was the monasteries that supplied hospitality to strangers and, as no charge was made for the accommodation, all travellers were expected to contribute according to their means to the Abbey funds. As more people began to travel they grouped themselves together, not only for the company but for mutual protection from highwaymen and robbers. Consequently, travellers arrived in groups at a monastery and it was often difficult to accommodate them all. In the early 19th century the concept of a hotel room was a sitting room in the front, a bedroom behind it and a storeroom to keep trunks behind the bedroom and this century is known as "Golden Age of Hotel of Hotels in Great Britain and the World", To overcome this, separate lodging houses called 'Inns' (a Saxon word) were built. The word 'Inn' came to mean a 'Lodging House' and until the passing of the Hotel Proprietors Act in 1956, it was the legal term for 'Hotel' and hotel proprietors were legally referred to as 'Common Innkeepers', 'Common' in this sense referred to Common Law. In the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries, manor houses, being hospitable places, willingly gave accommodation to travellers. As no payment was expected, travellers tipped the servants as a 'thank you' for the generous hospitality received-thus the practice of tipping was born.

The problems of hotel should not be neglected and there should be given some solutions. Counting of problems like cost, living quality and accessibility of hotel to main part of city.

Conclusion

Hospitality is one of the fundamental part of tourism while other consequences totally depends on it. Below two them given and there are possible solution of it.

1. Hiring staff- Solution

Training the new workforce on a regular basis is the only remedy available. Retaining a qualified staff requires you to employ a few tactics. For example, cultivating a feeling of belongingness (culture) and value for the team members will make them attached to their jobs and instill a sense of responsibility in their minds.

2. Change in marketing trends and dynamics-Marketing is one of the most common challenges faced by the hotel industry.

Engaging your guests on social media, messaging apps, and other online sources can work wonders and give you results in a few months. Implementing effective digital marketing strategies is a strong solution to such issues in the hospitality industry. Be consistent and patient with whatever tactics you apply. It is inevitable that with the right strategies.

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